

BARBITURATES. PART II. 5-METHYL-5-SUBSTITUTED BENZYL BARBITURATES AND THIOBARBITURATES

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Several 5-methyl-5-substituted benzyl barbiturates and thiobarbiturates as well as the substituted benzyl malonic esters required for the synthesis of above compounds have been prepared and described.

In continuation of our previous work (this issue, p. 661), barbiturates containing substituted benzyl group on C₅ have been synthesised and described in the present communication.

A few 5-alkyl-5-benzyl barbiturates were synthesised by John and Hill (*Amer. Chem. J.*, 1911, 46, 544) and Dox and Yoder (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1922, 44, 1141). 5-Ethyl-5-benzyl barbiturate was found to show convulsive properties. It has been observed that when the sum of C atoms in the groups at position-5 is larger than seven or eight, the hypnotic activity decreases and sometimes it leads to convulsions. The convulsive properties of 5-ethyl-5-benzyl barbiturate may perhaps be due to the sum of C atoms at position-5 exceeding eight C atoms. In the present work, barbiturates containing substituted benzyl and methyl groups on the C₅ atom have been prepared (sum total of C, not counting the nuclear substituents, is kept eight). The barbiturates were synthesised by the condensation of the appropriate methyl-substituted benzyl malonic ester with urea or thiourea.

EXPERIMENTAL

Substituted malonates were prepared by first benzylating and then methylating the ethylmalonic ester (Leuchs, *Ber.*, 1911, 44, 1509). The hitherto-unknown malonates are described in Table I.

Condensation of substituted malonates (0.1 M) with urea or thiourea (0.2 M) in presence of sodium ethylate (0.3 g. atom Na in 80 c.c. ethanol) was carried out as described in Part I (*loc. cit.*). The compounds are shown in Tables II and III with 25 to 30% yield

TABLE I
Substituted benzyl malonic esters.

Compound. X=	R=	B. P.	Ref. Index	Formula.	Found.	Calc.
<i>o</i> -Cl	H	140-48°/12 mm.	1.4880	C ₁₄ H ₁₇ O ₄ Cl	Cl : 12.4	12.5
<i>p</i> -Cl	H	188-90°/16	1.4975	"	"	"
<i>o</i> -Br	H	180°/12	1.4940	C ₁₄ H ₁₇ O ₄ Br	Br : 24.2	24.3
<i>m</i> -Br	H	173-80°/7	1.5289*	"	24.3	"
<i>p</i> -Br	H	185-86°/10	1.5090	"	"	"
<i>o</i> -CH ₃	H	168-70°/10	1.4920	C ₁₆ H ₂₀ O ₄	C : 64.0	62.2
<i>m</i> -CH ₃	H	180°/30	1.5052	"	H : 7.5	7.6
<i>p</i> -CH ₃	H	208°/20	1.5049	"	C : 68.1	
2 CH ₃ (3 : 4)	H	200°/60	1.4809*	C ₁₆ H ₂₀ O ₄	H : 7.5	
2 CH ₃ (2 : 4)	H	180-85°/20	1.4932	"	C : 69.0	69.1
2 CH ₃ (2 : 5)	H	174-76°/12	1.4890	"	H : 7.9	7.9
<i>o</i> -OCH ₃	H	194°/13	1.4950*	C ₁₅ H ₂₀ O ₅	C : 69.0	69.1
<i>p</i> -OCH ₃	H	202°/25	1.4946	"	H : 7.8	7.9
<i>o</i> -Cl	Me	140°/9	1.4960	C ₁₅ H ₁₉ O ₄ Cl	C : 69.0	69.1
<i>p</i> -Cl	"	195°/16	1.4918	"	H : 7.9	7.9
<i>o</i> -Br	"	196°/15	1.5120	C ₁₅ H ₁₉ O ₄ Br	C : 64.2	64.3
<i>m</i> -Br	"	198-200°/7	1.5327*	"	H : 7.1	7.1
<i>p</i> -Br	"	196°/11	1.5062	"	C : 64.1	64.3
<i>o</i> -CH ₃	"	182°/9	1.4812	C ₁₅ H ₂₀ O ₄	H : 7.1	7.1
<i>m</i> -CH ₃	"	180°/10	1.5420*	"	C : 64.1	64.3
<i>p</i> -CH ₃	"	220°/20	1.5328*	"	H : 7.1	7.1
2 CH ₃ (3 : 4)	"	222°/50	1.4932	C ₁₇ H ₂₄ O ₄	C : 64.1	64.3
2 CH ₃ (2 : 4)	"	206-208°/32	1.5108*	"	H : 7.1	7.1
2 CH ₃ (2 : 5)	"	182°/10	1.4880	"	C : 69.8	69.9
<i>o</i> -OCH ₃	"	196°/15	1.4918*	C ₁₆ H ₂₂ O ₅	H : 8.2	8.2
<i>p</i> -OCH ₃	"	220°/25	1.5132*	"	C : 65.3	65.3
					H : 7.4	7.5
					C : 65.2	65.3
					H : 7.4	7.5

Refractive indices were found at 27°; those marked with an asterisk were found at 38.5°.

TABLE II
5-Methyl-5-(substituted benzyl)-barbituric acids.

Compounds X=	M. P.	Formula.	% Nitrogen	
			Found.	Calc.
<i>o</i> -Cl	170°	C ₁₂ H ₁₁ O ₃ N ₃ Cl	10.4	10.5
<i>p</i> -Cl	197°	"	10.5	"
<i>o</i> -Br	151-52°	C ₁₇ H ₁₁ O ₃ N ₃ Br	9.0	9.0
<i>m</i> -Br	159-60°	"	8.9	"
<i>p</i> -Br	2-4°	"	9.0	"
<i>o</i> -CH ₃	134°	C ₁₃ H ₁₄ O ₃ N ₃	11.3	11.4
<i>m</i> -CH ₃	127-28°	"	"	"
<i>p</i> -CH ₃	Wax-like	"	"	"
2 CH ₃ (3:4)	175°	C ₁₄ H ₁₆ O ₃ N ₃	10.7	10.8
2 CH ₃ (2:4)	118°	"	"	"
2 CH ₃ (2:5)	78°	"	"	"
<i>o</i> -OCH ₃	168°	C ₁₃ H ₁₄ O ₄ N ₃	10.6	10.7
<i>p</i> -OCH ₃	252°	"	"	"

TABLE III
5-Methyl-5-(substituted benzyl)-2-thiobarbituric acids.

Compound. X=	M. P.	Formula.	% Nitrogen.	
			Found.	Calc.
<i>o</i> -Cl	112°	C ₁₂ H ₁₁ O ₂ N ₂ ClS	9.9	9.9
<i>p</i> -Cl	220°	"	"	"
<i>o</i> -Br	109-10°	C ₁₇ H ₁₁ O ₂ N ₂ BrS	8.5	8.6
<i>m</i> -Br	115°	"	"	"
<i>p</i> -Br	131-32°	"	"	"
<i>o</i> -CH ₃	116°	C ₁₃ H ₁₄ O ₂ N ₂ S	10.6	10.7
<i>m</i> -CH ₃	115°	"	"	"
<i>p</i> -CH ₃	114°	"	10.5	10.7
2 CH ₃ (3:4)	100°	C ₁₄ H ₁₆ O ₂ N ₂ S	10.0	10.1
2 CH ₃ (2:4)	120°	"	10.1	"
2 CH ₃ (2:5)	116°	"	"	"
<i>o</i> -OCH ₃	115°	C ₁₃ H ₁₄ O ₃ N ₂ S	10.0	10.1
<i>p</i> -OCH ₃	116°	"	"	"

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